

S2.

Publication timeline since Gross's 1973 description of *Pseudochazara sintenisi cingovskii*, including subsequent taxonomic changes and synonymies.

Gross F. 1973. *Satyrus sintenisi* auch in Europa, nebst Beschreibung einer neuen Unterart (Lep., Satyridae). — *Entomologische Zeitschrift* 83 (18): 211-214. ([url](#))

The source of the original taxonomic description of *Pseudochazara sintenisi cingovskii*. Later raised to species level.

Koutsaftikis A. 1974. Recent Butterfly Records from Greece. *Entomologist's Record and Journal of Variation* 86: 15-17. ([url](#))

Reporting *Pseudochazara sintenisi* Stgr. from Greece for the first time. The figure of a female specimen in this publication clearly depicts an individual that was later associated with *tisiphone*.

Brown J. 1976. A review of the genus *Pseudochazara* de Lesse, 1951 (Lep., Satyridae) in Greece. — *Entomologist's Gazette* 27: 85–90. ([url](#))

Establishing *P. cingovskii* Gross as a new status, with the holotype described from Mt. Smolikas. Describing the holotype from Mt. Smolikas.

Gross F. 1978. Beitrag zur Systematik von *Pseudochazara* Arten (Lep. Satyridae). — *Atalanta*, Würzburg 9: 41–103 ([url](#))

Discussing *P. cingovskii* from Yugoslav and Greek Macedonia. He did not assign the Greek population to any subspecies. The publication includes an illustration of the androconial cell of *P. cingovskii* from Prilep (present-day North Macedonia).

Brown J. [1981]. On the status of a little known satyrid butterfly from Greece. — *Entomologist's Record and Journal of Variation* 92(11/12): 280–281. ([url](#)).

Describing *P. cingovskii tisiphone* as a new subspecies.

De Prins W. & van der Poorten D. 1981. Een nieuwe *Pseudochazara*-soort voor de wetenschap uit Noordoost-Griekenland (Lepidoptera, Satyridae). — *Phegea* 10(1): 7–21. ([url](#))

Describing a new species of *Pseudochazara* from the Drama district (northeastern Greece): *Pseudochazara orestes* De Prins & van der Poorten, 1981.

Hesselbarth G., van Oorschot H. & Wagener S. 1995. *Die Tagfalter der Türkei unter Berücksichtigung der angrenzenden Länder*. — Selbstverlag Sigbert Wagener, Bocholt, Germany, 2201 p.

Reclassifying *P. cingovskii tisiphone* as *Pseudochazara mniszechii tisiphone* stat. nov., based on a single population near Bursa (Turkey) and from Greece.

Wakeham-Dawson A. 1997. Discriminant analysis of androconia in the genus *Pseudochazara* de Lesse, 1951 (Lepidoptera: Satyridae). — *Entomologist's Gazette* 48: 37-46. ([url](#))

Reclassifying *P. cingovskii tisiphone* as *Pseudochazara mniszechii tisiphone* stat. nov., independent of Hesselbarth *et al.* (1995).

Lukhtanov V. 2007. Nymphalidae: Satyrinae. In: Global Butterfly Names Project. Global Butterfly Names – <http://www.ucl.ac.uk/taxome/gbn/> (accessed on 07.iv.20)

Supporting *P. mniszechii tisiphone* (Brown, 1980).

Takáts K. & Mølgaard M. 2016. Partial mtCOI-sequences of Balkanic species of *Pseudochazara* (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae, Satyrinae) reveal three well-differentiated lineages. — *Entomologica romanica* **19**: 21–40 ([url](#))

First study on partial mtCOI-sequences of Balkanic species of *Pseudochazara*, also supporting the opinion, that *P. mniszechii tisiphone* is the valid taxon. In their study on partial mtCOI-sequences of Balkanic species of *Pseudochazara*, COI barcoding was used for the first time to confirm the classification.

Verovnik R. & Wiemers M. 2016. Species delimitation in the Grayling genus *Pseudochazara* (Lepidoptera, Nymphalidae, Satyrinae) supported by DNA barcodes. — *Zookeys* **600**: 131–154. doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.600.7798

Species delimitation in *Pseudochazara* supported by DNA barcodes, based on a deep genetic split between *P. mniszechii* and *P. mniszechii tisiphone*, elevated the latter to species level

Cuvelier S., Parmentier L., Papparisto A. & Couckuyt J. 2018. Butterflies of Albania – Fluturat e Shqipërisë. New surveys, new species and a new checklist (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea). — *Phegea* **46**(2): 48-69. ([url](#))

Reporting, for the first time, a new disjunct population of *P. tisiphone* in Dibër County.

Dincă V., Dapporto L., Somervuo P., Vodă R., Cuvelier S., Gascoigne-Pees M., Huemer P., Mutanen M., Hebert P. & Vila R. 2021. High resolution DNA barcode library for European butterflies reveals continental patterns of mitochondrial genetic diversity. Supplementary data 14. — *Communications Biology* **4**, 315. ([url](#))

Neighbor-joining tree of 22,306 COI sequences used in the study, including for the first time *P. tisiphone* from Dibër County.

Dapporto L., Menchetti M., Vodă R., Corbella C., Cuvelier S., Djemadi I., Gascoigne-Pees M., Hinojosa J., Lam N., Serracanta M., Talavera G., Dincă V. & Vila. R. 2022. The Atlas of mitochondrial diversity of Western Palearctic butterflies. Appendix S1. — *Global Ecology and Biogeography*. **00**, 1–7. ([url](#))

Documented COI gene diversity in Balkan *Pseudochazara* as part of The Atlas of Mitochondrial Diversity of Western Palearctic Butterflies.

Cuvelier S. 2023. Albania, a country with unexpected, intraspecific genetic variability in butterflies (Papilionoidea: Nymphalidae & Lycaenidae). Balancing on a tightrope between species, subspecies, ESU's and haplotypes. — *Lépidoptères* **32**(82): 32-40. ([url](#))

Providing further commentary on the IGV Atlas regarding *P. tisiphone* and designated the population in Dibër County as a distinct Evolutionarily Significant Unit (ESU).

Cuvelier S. & Marafi AJ M. 2025. Status and conservation of genetic diversity in the disjunct populations of *Pseudochazara tisiphone* Brown, [1981], in Albania. — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* **2025**(1): 71-78. ([pdf](#)) ([url](#))

Assigning the population in Dibër County the subspecies status as *Pseudochazara tisiphone dibra* ssp. nov. and registering this new subspecies in ZooBank.

Parmentier L. & Qirinxhi X. 2025. Unexpected cryptic diversity revealed through integrative analysis within isolated populations of the Graylings (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae: Satyrinae) in the Western Balkans — *Phegea* **53**(1) 22-38. (accessed via Figshare on 02.iii.2025, [version 2](#)).

Elevating, independently of Cuvelier & Marafi (2025), the population in Dibër County to species level, naming it *Pseudochazara misjai* sp. nov. and registering in ZooBank.

Cuvelier S., Marafi AJ M. & Papparisto A. 2025. Synonymy of *Pseudochazara misjai* and *Pseudochazara tisiphone dibra*: taxonomic reassessment of an Albanian butterfly population. Is the glass half full or half empty? An inconvenient truth. — *Archives of Western Palearctic Lepidoptera* **2025**(2): 1-20. ([pdf](#)) ([online](#))

Reassessing the taxonomic status of the population, critically evaluating the evidence supporting both descriptions. Based on a careful review of morphological, climatic, ecological, and molecular data, it is proposed that *Pseudochazara misjai* is a junior synonym of *Pseudochazara tisiphone dibra*, which should remain the valid name for the population. This decision follows the guidelines of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN), prioritizing the earlier description to maintain nomenclatural stability.